

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: SALL4.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of SALL4 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in human embryonic
11 stem cells.

12 Citations

13 1. Zhang, J., Tam, W.L., Tong, G.Q., Wu, Q., Chan, H.Y., Soh, B.S., Lou, Y., Yang, J., Ma, Y., Chai, L.
14 and Ng, H.H., 2006. Sall4 modulates embryonic stem cell pluripotency and early embryonic development
15 by the transcriptional regulation of Pou5f1. *Nature cell biology*, 8(10), pp.1114-1123.

16 2. Yang, J., Chai, L., Fowles, T.C., Alipio, Z., Xu, D., Fink, L.M., Ward, D.C. and Ma, Y., 2008.
17 Genome-wide analysis reveals Sall4 to be a major regulator of pluripotency in murine-embryonic stem
18 cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 105(50), pp.19756-19761.